

PREPARATION OF CARBON FIBER SIZING AGENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF ITS PROPERTIES

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Keywords: Improved epoxy functional emulsifier, Carbon fibers, Sizing agent, Aqueous,

ABSTRACT

A sizing agent for carbon fiber comprising a component (A) and a component (B) and a component (C), each of which is described below. Component (A): a carboxylic acid type surfactant with at least one carboxyl group within each molecule, and with a acid value of 20 to 40mgKOH/g; Component (B): a diamine compound with at least one primary amine group within each molecule; Component (C): an epoxy compound with at least two epoxy group within each molecule, the epoxy value of which is about from 0.2 ~ 0.6. The invention relates to improved epoxy functional surfactants prepared by reaction of an epoxy composition and an amidoamine composition formed from a blend of acid-terminated polyoxyalkylene polyols. The improved epoxy functional surfactants may be reacted with an excess of epoxy composition and water to result in an aqueous dispersion. The amidoamine composition may be a reaction mixture of a diamine compound and an acid terminated polyoxyalkylene composition formed from two or more polyoxyalkylene polyol compounds.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibers are lightweight and excellent in strength and elastic modulus, and thus are combined with various matrix resins to form composite materials^[1, 2], which are used in various fields including aircraft members, spacecraft members, automobile members, ship members, constructional materials, and sporting goods. Carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy (CFRE) matrix composites^[3, 4] have been widely used among those composite materials. However, the surface of CF is inert, which may result in poor wettability^[5] and poor interfacial bond between the fibers and the epoxy matrix. To solve this problem, a series of methods are attempted, such as electrochemical oxidation, plasma treatment, gas phase oxidation, radiation and sizing treatment. Among these methods, sizing treatment shows predominant advantages for practical applications such as simplicity and flexibility. The sizing agent^[6], which is the interface of the carbon fiber and the epoxy matrix, can protect the fiber surface, improve the handle ability in processing, provide the functional groups on fiber surface and enhance compatibility between carbon fiber and epoxy resins.

Aqueous sizing agent of epoxy resins have been known for many years. It is reported that waterborne epoxy emulsion can be prepared by solvent method, phase reversing and self-emulsification method^[7]. Water-based epoxy emulsion^[8] obtained by solvent method because of the presence of organic solvents, such as acetone and toluene, which cause environmental pollution and affect human health. With the strengthening of environmental awareness, waterborne epoxy resin sizing agent made by self-emulsification method has attracted much attention in recent years due to environmentally friendly and low VOC. Meanwhile, the sizing agent prepared by self-emulsification has small particle size and narrow distribution^[9] without precipitation and demulsification compared with the phase reversing. Furthermore, the emulsifier can participate in the reaction without the problems caused by the addition of external surfactant. Therefore, most of the waterborne epoxy emulsion synthesized by self-emulsification method exhibit excellent storage stability and dilution stability.

In order to make the epoxy resin into aqueous emulsion and maintain a certain stability, we need a surfactant^[10] which can react with the hydrophobic epoxy resin and introduce hydrophilic segments. Therefore, we have synthesized an emulsifier with epoxy groups at both ends in this article using polyethylene glycol (PEG). We know about that the reactivity of the hydroxyl^[11] with epoxy group is weakly, especially the molecular weight is relatively large, such as PEG6000 and PEG8000. However, the hydrophilic segments are too few to emulsify the hydrophobic epoxy with low molecular weight PEG, such as PEG400 and PEG600. As a result, PEG4000 selected as a raw material. The waterborne epoxy sizing agent has a particle size between 50 and 100 nm with our improved emulsifier. Furthermore, the storage stability and the dilution stability are predominant without precipitation and demulsification. Simultaneously, the wettability between the carbon fiber and the resin is improved, and the comprehensive performance of the composite material is improved.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Material

Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (E-1001, E-828) was supplied from Nanya Epoxy Resin Co., Ltd.

PEG(400,800,2000,4000,6000,8000) was supplied from The DOW Chemical Company Co., Ltd

2-methyl-1,5-pentanediamine was purchased from Beijing Reagent Co., Ltd

2.2 Preparation of the improved epoxy functional emulsifier

Herein, the preparation method and characterization of the sizing agent are described. Firstly, we turn the hydroxyl groups at both ends of the PEG into carboxyl groups with oxidation method or bromide method. Secondly, the amidoamine composition made by carboxyl groups and diamine compound as a result of the reactivity of the hydroxyl group or the carboxyl group with the epoxy group are weakly. Finally, the improved epoxy functional emulsifier is made by the reaction of the amidoamine composition and the corresponding epoxy resin. The improved epoxy functional emulsifier can react with excess epoxy composition and water to result in an aqueous dispersion.

Figure 1 is the reaction process of the improved epoxy functional emulsifier. The most sticking point is the oxidation of hydroxyl groups. And the figure 2 is the infrared spectra of PEG before and after oxidation. We can see clearly from the infrared comparison chart, there is an infrared absorption peak which appears at 1715cm^{-1} after oxidation. As a result of the absorption peak of carboxyl groups is from 1700cm^{-1} to 1720cm^{-1} , we can determine that the hydroxyl group has been converted to carboxyl. Meanwhile, we monitor the reaction process and the conversion rate by the acid value of the product. The acid value increases with time and the acid value of the final product is about 24.56mgKOH/g , corresponding to conversion of 87.7% of the hydroxyl groups to carboxyl. And then the subsequent reaction is followed by oxidized PEG (COOH-PEG-COOH).

The following is the detailed illustration of the reaction process and infrared spectra of PEG before and after oxidation:

Figure 1: the reaction process of the improved epoxy functional emulsifier

Figure 2: Infrared spectra of PEG before and after oxidation

2.3 Characterization of aqueous emulsions

In order to select the appropriate PEG to enhance the stability of the emulsion, different molecular weight PEG was modified in table 1.

PEG	Mn	Mw	Acid value (mgKOH/g)	Conversion rate	Emulsion properties
PEG-400	375	452	270.28	90.31%	hydrophobic
PEG-800	788	847	128.85	90.49%	precipitation
PEG-2000	1847	2114	53.76	88.49%	precipitation
PEG-4000	3870	4341	25.43	87.71%	uniform and stable
PEG-6000	5879	6133	13.35	69.97%	precipitation
PEG-8000	7692	8251	8.11	55.62%	hydrophobic

Table 1: Effect of different PEG on emulsion properties

Table 1 is the effect of different molecular weight PEG on emulsion properties. If the molecular weight is relatively low, such as PEG-400 and PEG-800, the stability of the emulsion is poor or even hydrophobic. Although the reactivity is high and the acid value is large, the content of the hydrophilic segment is too low to emulsify the epoxy resin. Simultaneously, the reactivity decreases significantly with increasing molecular weight, such as PEG-6000 or PEG-8000. PEG with relatively high molecular weight can not be connected to the epoxy resin, which is just a thickener rather than an emulsifier. Therefore, improved epoxy functional emulsifier PEG-4000 was selected for subsequent experiments.

The particle size of the emulsion and the viscosity after drying are also important, so we improved the performance of the emulsion by changing the ratio of epikote828 and epikote1001.

Table 2 is the particle size and particle size distribution of different composition. Small particle size can fill the groove on the surface of the carbon fiber, which can reduce the

generation of fluff and enhance the processing performance of carbon fiber. At the same time, the viscosity after drying increase significantly with the increase in the amount of epikote1001, which can enhance the integrity of carbon fiber and properties of the carbon fiber reinforced composite material.

E(828):E(1001)	Particle size/nm	Particle size distribution
100(E-828)	55.48	31.25
20:80	56.76	33.71
40:60	67.81	32.47
60:80	76.49	34.12
80:20	82.61	32.59
100(E-1001)	91.17	35.27

Table 2: the particle size and particle size distribution of different composition

Furthermore, we can deduce that the distribution of particles is narrow and uniform from the TEM micrographs.

Figure 3: TEM of the water-based epoxy emulsion

3 CONCLUSION

An improved epoxy functional emulsifier is synthesized in this paper with PEG, which has two epoxy functional groups at both ends. And the emulsifier can participate in the reaction without the problems caused by the addition of external surfactant. The particle size of the water-based epoxy emulsion is from 50nm to 100nm and the viscosity is high enough because of the epikote1001, which is help to reduce the generation of fluff and enhance the integrity of carbon fiber. Furthermore, the storage stability and the dilution stability is well without precipitation or demulsification. The property of the carbon fiber sized with our sizing agent has been significantly improved.

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